

The Prevalence and Impact of Painful Diabetic Neuropathy on Quality of Life and Pattern of Drug Usage for the Alleviation of Neuropathic Pain in Kerala, India - Cross-Sectional Survey Analysis

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Abstract

Painful diabetic neuropathy (PDN) is a frequent and debilitating complication of diabetes mellitus, significantly affecting the quality of life of the patient as well as their family. The therapeutic burden of this ailment contributes to a socioeconomic burden on the community. Different therapeutic agents with varying therapeutic and adverse profiles are available to manage this condition. The usage of these therapeutic agents depends on prescribers' clinical experience and understanding. This study aims to evaluate the prevalence of PDN, its impact on the quality of life, and the patterns of drug usage for neuropathic pain alleviation in Kerala, India. Data were collected from diabetic clinics across Kerala through surveys and medical records. The data analysis of this cross-sectional survey analysis indicates a high prevalence of PDN, with substantial impacts on both the physical mental, and socio-economic well-being of the patients affected. Most physicians reliance on a variety of pharmacological treatments, predominantly gabapentinoids, and antidepressants. The findings highlight the need for enhanced pain management strategies and increased awareness of PDN among healthcare providers and patients.

Keywords: Diabetic Neuropathy, Painful Neuropathy, Quality of Life, Treatment Of Neuropathy.

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Introduction

Rapid socioeconomic development and demographic changes, along with increased susceptibility for Indian individuals, have led to the explosive increase in the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in India over the past four decades and made her one of the epicenters of diabetes mellitus. Type 2 diabetes mellitus in Asian Indian people is characterized by a young age of onset and occurrence at low levels of BMI, have more susceptibility to the complications of diabetes mellitus differs from that of white populations [1,2]. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a growing public health concern worldwide, with a particularly high prevalence in India [1,3].

One of the most severe complications of diabetes is diabetic neuropathy (DN), which affects the peripheral nerves and can lead to painful diabetic neuropathy (PDN) [4]. A definition of peripheral neuropathic pain (NP) in diabetes, adapted from a definition recently proposed by the International Association for the Study of Pain [4,5], is "pain arising as a direct consequence of abnormalities in the peripheral somatosensory system in people with diabetes." The prevalence of NP in the diabetic population is roughly estimated between 3 and 25%

of patients who might experience NP[3]. Based on available studies, the prevalence of pain ranges from 40% to 50% in those with diabetic neuropathy. It can be disabling and devastating, with a significant impact on the patient's quality of life and associated healthcare costs. Pathophysiologic mechanisms underlying PDN are similar to other neuropathic pain disorders and broadly invoke peripheral and central sensitization [7]. Thus, PDN is characterized by chronic pain that significantly impairs the quality of life of affected individuals. Kerala, a state in southern India, has one of the highest rates of diabetes in the country[8]. Despite this, there is limited data on the prevalence and impact of PDN in this region, as well as on the patterns of drug usage for its management. This study aims to address this gap by investigating these aspects in Kerala.

Methodology

Study Design and Participants: This cross-sectional study was conducted in various diabetic clinics across Kerala, after the completion of Institutional Ethical Committee approval. A total of 964 diabetic patients, aged 18 and above, were

recruited. Inclusion criteria included a confirmed diagnosis of diabetes for at least one year and the presence of neuropathic symptoms. Patients with other causes of neuropathy were excluded.

Data Collection: Data were collected through structured questionnaires and medical record reviews. The questionnaire included sections on demographic information, diabetes history, neuropathic symptoms, pain assessment (using the Visual Analog Scale), and impact on quality of life (using the SF-36 questionnaire). Information on pharmacological treatments for PDN was also collected.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Prevalence rates of PDN were calculated, and the impact on quality of life was assessed using SF-36 scores. The pattern of drug usage was analyzed to determine the most commonly prescribed medications.

Results

Prevalence of PDN: Out of the 964 diabetic patients surveyed, 45% were found to have PDN, indicating a high prevalence in this population. PDN was more common among older adults and those with a longer duration of diabetes.

Impact on Quality of Life: Patients with PDN reported significantly lower SF-36 scores, particularly in the domains of physical functioning, bodily pain, and general health perceptions. Mental health scores were also adversely affected, with many patients reporting feelings of depression and anxiety related to their chronic pain.

Patterns of Drug Usage: The most commonly prescribed medications for PDN in Kerala were gabapentinoids (particularly gabapentin and pregabalin) and antidepressants (such as amitriptyline and duloxetine). Other medications included anticonvulsants, opioids, and topical agents. Combination therapy was frequently used to manage symptoms more effectively.

Figure 1:

Discussion & Conclusion: Polyneuropathy is one of the most common complications of long-standing diabetes. Progressive sensory loss can predispose patients to foot ulcers and the neuropathy often causes pain which can significantly affect patients' quality of life [9]. The presence of PDN was found to negatively influence the health-related quality of life of type II diabetic patients with the greatest impact being on the 'role physical' and 'mental health' domains. Older age, presence of diabetes-related complications, and longer duration of illness negatively influenced the health-related quality of life [9]. The significant impact on quality of life highlights the importance of addressing both physical and psychological aspects of PDN. The high incidence of PDN, and severe complications of diabetes mellitus, significantly compromise patients' quality of life and at the same time cause tremendous economic

burden to patient's families as well as the community. Considering drug costs becomes part of treatment decisions, with the growing choice of monotherapy or combination treatment strategies for PDN treatment [10]. The high prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Kerala underscores the need for enhanced screening for diabetes-related complications such as PDN and framing of management strategies.

The management of diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) comprises excluding other causes for painful peripheral neuropathy, effective diabetic control, and the use of pharmacological agents to alleviate pain. However, the definite relationship between glycaemic control and the development and severity of DPN remains controversial. In this context, the mainstay of PDN management continues to be symptomatic control of pain with drugs. Several placebo-controlled studies have

shown that opioids, antiepileptic, and antidepressant drugs together with capsaicin are effective for alleviating pain in PDN. The opioid agents such as tramadol and oxycodone are effective but their adverse effects, such as constipation and physical dependency, may limit their usefulness as a first-line treatment for PDN [11]. Among the antidepressant drugs, tricyclic agents are effective for symptomatic improvement in PDN and are widely used, however, their nonspecific actions like anticholinergic and sedative properties limit their usage. There is also good evidence that the serotonin-noradrenaline reuptake inhibitor antidepressant drugs venlafaxine and duloxetine are effective in treating PDN [11]. Topiramate, lamotrigine, sodium valproate, and oxcarbazepine are effective in smaller studies but do not have the same evidence base as the gabapentinoid group of drugs. Of the newer antiepileptic drugs, lacosamide appears to be the most promising for alleviating DPN. Capsaicin has the best evidence base of all the topical agents, but local anesthetic patches may also have a useful therapeutic role. It is not possible to nominate a single drug as the first-line treatment for PDN and there is evidence that a low-dose combination of two or more drugs rather than a single agent may provide better symptomatic relief with fewer adverse effects. Further studies are necessary to clarify the best combination(s) of treatment for PDN [12].

The gabapentinoid group of drugs, gabapentin and pregabalin, appear to be the most evidence-based of the antiepileptic drugs for treating DPN. Large placebo-controlled studies have been performed with both of these agents. For many patients, it is still unclear what advantages pregabalin has over gabapentin for DPN [12]. The predominant use of gabapentinoids and antidepressants aligns with global treatment guidelines, although the variability in drug usage suggests a need for standardized treatment protocols [13,14]. This study reveals a high prevalence of PDN among diabetic patients in Kerala and its substantial impact on quality of life. The findings call for improved awareness and management strategies to alleviate the burden of PDN. Future research should focus on long-term outcomes of different treatment modalities and the development of comprehensive pain management programs tailored to the needs of this population.

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References

1. Unnikrishnan, R., Anjana, R. M., & Mohan, V. (2016). Diabetes mellitus and its complications

in India. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 12(6), 357-370.

2. Mohan, V., et al. (2007). Epidemiology of type 2 diabetes: Indian scenario. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 125(3), 217-230.
3. Boulton, A. J., et al. (2014). Diabetic neuropathies: a statement by the American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes Care*, 37(10), 2867-2879.
4. Tesfaye, S., et al. (2011). Diabetic peripheral neuropathy: a clinical guide. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, 27(7), 629-638
5. Tesfaye, S., Boulton, A. J., Dyck, P. J., Freeman, R., Horowitz, M., Kempner, P., & Vinik, A. (2010). Diabetic neuropathies: update on definitions, diagnostic criteria, estimation of severity, and treatments. *Diabetes Care*, 33(10), 2285-2293.
6. Treede RD, Jensen TS, Campbell JN, Cruccu G, Dostrovsky JO, Griffin JW, Hansson P, Hughes R, Nurmikko T, Serra J: Neuropathic pain: redefinition and a grading system for clinical and research purposes. *Neurology* 2008;70:1630–1635.
7. T. Didangelos *et al.* Painful diabetic neuropathy: clinical aspects *Handb. Clin. Neurol.* (2014).
8. Vijayakumar, G., Manghat, S., Vijayakumar, R. *et al.* Incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus and prediabetes in Kerala, India: results from a 10-year prospective cohort. *BMC Public Health* 19, 140 (2019).
9. Degu H, Wondimagegnehu A, Yifru YM, Belachew A. Is health related quality of life influenced by diabetic neuropathic pain among type II diabetes mellitus patients in Ethiopia? *PLoS One*. 2019 Feb 4;14(2):e0211449.
10. Zhu J, Li W, Shi C, Li Q. A pharmacoeconomic evaluation of the pharmacotherapeutic options for painful diabetic neuropathy. *Expert Opin Pharmacother.* 2022 Apr;23(5):551-559.
11. Chong MS, Hester J. Diabetic painful neuropathy: current and future treatment options. *Drugs.* 2007;67(4):569-85.
12. Chong MS, Hester J. Diabetic painful neuropathy: current and future treatment options. *Drugs.* 2007;67(4):569-85.
13. Kremer M, Salvat E, Muller A, Yalcin I, Barrot M. Antidepressants and gabapentinoids in neuropathic pain: Mechanistic insights. *Neuroscience.* 2016 Dec 3;338:183-206.
14. Callaghan, B. C., et al. (2012). Diabetic neuropathy: clinical manifestations and current treatments. *The Lancet Neurology*, 11(6), 521-534.